

Indicators to assess safety performance: A literature review on safety culture in industry and construction sectors

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Abstract: This literature review explores the diverse definitions and measurement approaches for the use of safety performance (SP) indicators in the industrial and construction sectors. SP indicators are crucial for organizations to implement appropriate risk management measures and prevent workplace accidents. However, there is no consensus on a sufficiently comprehensive measure for evaluating SP. This literature review, which is a secondary review based on a systematic review of the literature on occupational safety culture (SC), includes data extracted from 33 articles published between 2016 and 2020 in the industrial and construction sectors, sourced from the Web of Science and Scopus databases. Specifically, 25 SP variables, such as workplace accidents, injuries, safety behaviors and personnel safety motivation, were identified. These variables were categorized into positive indicators, which reflect gains for the organization (safety promoting factors), and negative indicators, which reflect losses in the system and areas needing mitigation (error enforcing factors). The results are discussed in terms of their implications for evaluating SP, illustrating the existing variability in the definition and operationalization of SP indicators, contributing to the rationale of future applications and improvements of the organizational SP. This review emphasizes the need for a dynamic approach to SP evaluation, incorporating both positive and negative indicators. The findings highlight the necessity for a comprehensive and adaptive framework to improve safety measures and outcomes in workplace environments.

Keywords: Safety performance, Indicators, Accidents, Risks, Workplace.

Indicadores para avaliar o desempenho de segurança: Uma revisão da literatura sobre a cultura de segurança nos setores da indústria e da construção

Resumo: Esta revisão de literatura explora as diversas definições e abordagens de avaliação na utilização de indicadores de desempenho de segurança (DS) nos setores da indústria e construção. Os indicadores de DS são fundamentais para que as organizações implementem medidas apropriadas de gestão de riscos e previnam acidentes de trabalho. No entanto, não há consenso sobre uma medida suficientemente abrangente para avaliar o DS. Esta revisão de literatura, que é uma revisão secundária baseada numa revisão sistemática da literatura sobre cultura de segurança ocupacional, inclui dados extraídos de 33 artigos publicados entre 2016 e 2020 nos setores da indústria e construção, obtidos das bases de dados Web of Science e Scopus. Especificamente, foram identificadas 25 variáveis de DS, tais como acidentes de trabalho, lesões, comportamentos de segurança e motivação dos trabalhadores para a segurança. Estas variáveis foram categorizadas em indicadores positivos, que refletem ganhos para a organização (fatores que promovem a segurança), e indicadores negativos, que refletem perdas no sistema e áreas que necessitam ser mitigadas (fatores que reforçam erros). Os resultados são discutidos em termos das suas implicações para a avaliação do DS, ilustrando a variabilidade existente na definição e operacionalização dos indicadores de DS, contribuindo para a fundamentação de futuras aplicações e melhorias do DS organizacional. Esta revisão enfatiza a necessidade de uma abordagem dinâmica para a avaliação do DS, incorporando tanto indicadores positivos como negativos. As conclusões destacam a necessidade de um quadro abrangente e adaptativo para melhorar as medidas de segurança e os resultados no local de trabalho.

Palavras-chave: Desempenho de segurança, Indicadores, Acidentes, Riscos, Local de trabalho.

1. Introduction

The topic of safety culture (SC) has garnered significant interest from different industries and corporations (Fleming et al., 2018; van Nunen et al., 2018). This heightened focus is driven by the recognition of SC's essential role in mitigating and preventing potential disasters (Ahmad et al., 2022; Cooper, 2000; Siuta et al., 2022; Tetzlaff et al., 2021), as well as the persistently high rates of workplace accidents in many sectors, particularly in industry and construction (Ahmad et al., 2022; Eurostat, 2022). Fostering and strengthening a robust SC is critical for enhancing organizational safety performance (SP). A strong SC promotes the effective deployment of safety management resources and practices, shaping the work environment and significantly impacting the attitudes and behaviors of workers (Ahmad et al., 2022; Siuta et al., 2022; Tappura et al., 2022).

The evolution of industries to meet increasingly complex requirements and shorter deadlines poses new challenges in terms of occupational safety (Kadir et al., 2022; Wanberg et al., 2013). Stricter risk management and SP criteria are imposed, putting pressure on managers to find a balance between efficiency and safety (Kadir et al., 2022; Oduoza, 2020). Nonetheless, occupational safety remains an underestimated concern in many organizations, where the pressure for productivity can lead to risky working practices (Swuste et al., 2012). The non-routine nature of activities, especially in construction but also in industry (due to job rotation to avoid pressure and possible occupational injuries/illnesses for workers), makes safety management systems more challenging and difficult to plan and control, increasing vulnerability to unforeseen risks (Magalhães et al., 2022; Oduoza, 2020).

SP has been defined in diverse ways, but it tends to reflect measurable outcomes resulting from the operation of a safety and health management system (NP ISO 45001, 2019). Effective SP management ensures that an organization's processes are conducted in a manner consistent with the goal of achieving safety objectives. One way to accomplish this is by establishing performance indicators as tools to gauge the organization's SP (Stanivuk et al., 2022). These indicators help determine whether the organizations are taking appropriate initiatives and defining risk management measures to prevent workplace injuries and fatalities (Shaikh et al., 2021). They are used to measure and evaluate the quality and effectiveness of actions to promote workers' health, safety, and well-being in the work environment. Therefore, understanding the determinants of workers' SP can lead to better occupational safety (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014).

In recent decades, there have been several investigations on indicators that can assist the evaluation of SP (Barbosa et al., 2019; Bellamy & Sol, 2012; Louvar, 2010; Shaikh et al., 2021; Vosoughi et al., 2021), from work accident rates to actions or behaviors that promote health and safety at work (Vosoughi et al., 2021). Indicators can be defined as tools that measure specific attributes by assigning values to a particular situational context. They convey significance, reflecting a specific reality, whether simple or complex, and providing a representation of assessment. They have gained notable significance across various contexts as a means to comprehend the patterns and potential outcomes of circumstances and situations (Prado & Castanha, 2020). Indicators can be defined as qualitative or quantitative measures aimed at obtaining information about a particular subject under study (Barbosa et al., 2019). Quantitative indicators relate to statistics, facts, measurements, and/or quantitative data series, while qualitative indicators refer to a set of postulated evidence or perceptions about reality (Mourão, 2006). This dual adaptability in the structure facilitates compliance with regulations through the selection of

suitable methodological approaches, whether quantitative, qualitative, or both (Prado & Castanha, 2020).

Despite various investigations on the determinants of SP (e.g., Barbosa et al., 2019; Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014; Shaikh et al., 2021; Vosoughi et al., 2021), these studies have not produced consensus. The lack of a tailored and appropriate measure to assess SP is a limitation associated with evaluating the effectiveness of different safety programs (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014). For this reason, there has been a growing concern among organizations for SP indicators to adopt a more dynamic approach to manage safety-related requests, as well as to contribute in predicting latent hazards, anticipating the occurrence of injuries and/or deaths. Historically, SP has been evaluated using metrics that measure incidents that have already occurred, such as accident and injury rates, incidents, and financial losses. These are referred in the literature as lagging or reactive indicators (Middlesworth, 2023; Yorio et al., 2020). They are used to track the compliance with safety rules as well as to provide a bottom-line evaluation of safety effectiveness at a facility (Middlesworth, 2023; OSHA, 2019). While these metrics are important for understanding how many people were injured and the severity of the incidents, they don't provide insight into how well a company is preventing incidents and accidents (Yorio et al., 2020). Therefore, leading indicators (also known as proactive indicators) should also be considered, as they can help identify potential safety risks and prevent incidents before they occur (Government of Alberta, 2020; OSHA, 2019). Leading indicators are preventive, predictive, and proactive measures, which provide insight into the effective performance of safety and health activities (Government of Alberta, 2020). Unlike reactive indicators, which measure past events such as injuries and illnesses, proactive indicators measure events leading to incidents and can identify potential problems in a safety and health program, allowing the organizations to take active steps to address potential safety risks, besides preventing incidents from occurring (OSHA, 2019).

Leading indicators support proactive investigation, contrasting with the reactive approach of lagging indicators. Recent research demonstrates that leading indicators are more effective than their lagging counterparts (Salas & Hallowell, 2016; Versteeg et al., 2019), providing superior insights into SP since they serve as proactive tools for evaluating project safety (Guo & Yiu, 2015; Wehle & Issa, 2016). It is important to note, however, that the dichotomy between reactive and proactive indicators cannot be addressed in a linear way. Current scientific data acknowledges the use of both types of indicators, but it is agreed that there should not be excessive concern with this distinction as it is not linear (e.g., Bayramova et al., 2023; Haas & Yorio, 2016; Oswald, 2019). The classification of indicators depends on their type, context, and timing of use. An indicator can be reactive in one circumstance and proactive in another, and vice versa (Bayramova et al., 2023; Haas & Yorio, 2016; Oswald, 2019; Sheehan et al., 2016). For instance, an indicator may be reactive in its origin, but if used to prevent future events and encourage contingency actions, it assumes a proactive nature. Similarly, a proactive indicator that is not used preventively becomes merely a record, assuming a reactive nature (Bayramova et al., 2023).

For that reason, indicators should measure things that might one day become precursors to harm, as well as things that contribute to safety in positive terms. However, shifting the commonly held mindset that focuses solely on error prevention and mistake reduction is necessary. To transform the perspective towards the organization's potential for safety, a combination of positive factors is essential (Reiman, 2010; Reiman &

Pietikäinen, 2012). The transition from a negative to a positive outlook on organizational safety potential is crucial for assessing the presence of key requirements within an organization (Reiman & Pietikäinen, 2012). This approach emphasizes the direction of change and offers a clearer understanding of how indicators affect safety outcomes (Golabchi et al., 2024). Merely recognizing the absence of fatigue or complacency is insufficient; it is also essential to monitor and enhance the positive elements within the organization. Positive SP indicators play a vital role in both tracking and fostering the system safety (Szabo & Kloben, 2020).

Considering on the above, differentiating between positive indicators (safety promoting factors) and negative indicators (error enforcing factors) can be a good way to address safety factors (Reiman & Pietikäinen, 2012). Positive indicators highlight safety successes and areas of improvement (Ali et al., 2022; Bai & Liu, 2023; Golabchi et al., 2024; Lingard et al., 2017), while negative indicators point out areas needing attention and mitigation (Bai & Liu, 2023; Golabchi et al., 2024; Lingard et al., 2017). This typology categorizes indicators identified in this literature review, since it reflects gains and losses in the safety system and emphasizes the need for a comprehensive and adaptive approach to SP evaluation.

Given these insights, this literature review seeks to identify indicators presented in the literature to assess SP. The fundamental aim is to comprehend how SP is operationalized, identifying the variables used to assess it, considering the positive and negative typology. The articles reviewed stem from a systematic literature review previously conducted. While the systematic review identified variables of safety culture/climate and the safety management system (SMS) (from the industry and construction sectors) that influence SP, this study sought to identify and evaluate SP variables.

2. Methodology

The present review is a secondary review/analysis, emerging from a systematic literature review on occupational SC (Pinto & Silva, 2023). To better understand how the articles included in this review were selected, it is important to clarify some aspects regarding the systematic literature review, specifically that it was conducted according to the PRISMA protocol (Moher et al., 2009), during the year of 2021 and covered publications from January 2016 to December 2020. For identification of manuscripts, searches were conducted in the Web of Science (Core Collection + Proceedings) and Scopus databases using keywords related to SC, safety climate, and SMS in the industry and construction sectors (giving the high number of occupational accidents reported in these sectors) (Eurostat, 2022). During the screening phase, the authors independently analyzed titles and abstracts, excluding manuscripts that did not address factors associated to safety culture/climate and SMS that influence SP. Manuscripts were evaluated against inclusion and exclusion criteria. Only original empirical studies published in English or Portuguese during the last five years (from 2016 to 2020, considering the moment when the initial phase of the literature review was performed) that focus on the industry and construction sectors and analyze the relationship between identified factors and SP were include), focusing on industry and construction sectors, and analyzing the relationship between identified factors and SP, were included. Exclusions were made for non-original research, studies outside the defined sectors, editorials, reviews, and articles without available abstracts or full texts.

Out of 379 articles initially identified, 33 articles were included in the systematic review. They cover a range of countries, totaling 24 nations. Regarding the sectors under analysis, 16 studies focused on the industry sector, while 17 addressed the construction sector. Most of the research adopted a quantitative study design, although a significant presence of qualitative studies and studies combining both approaches were observed. The majority of investigations were conducted among workers.

The systematic review only looked at the dimensions of safety culture/climate and SMS that could influence SP. Therefore, for the present study, the authors analyzed how the SP construct was operationalized in the articles that were part of the systematic literature review. Qualitative content analysis (Amado, 2000) was used to analyze the indicators of SP identified in each study. This analysis process was discussed by both researchers, and disagreements in the categorization were discussed in order to reach a consensual resolution. Each operationalization of SP made in the studies was analyzed. Based on this analysis, the respective variable was integrated into a category of indicators.

The indicators were categorized according to a typology found in the literature, which distinguishes between safety promoting factors (positive indicators) that reflect gains and improvements in the safety system and error inducing factors (negative indicators) that represent losses within the safety system (cf., Bai & Liu, 2023; Golabchi et al., 2024; Lingard et al., 2017; Reiman & Pietikäinen, 2012).

3. Results

The analysis of the 33 articles allowed for the identification of 25 SP variables, categorized into safety promoting factors (positive indicators) and error inducing factors (negative indicators), as detailed above. It is important to highlight that these categorizations were made by the authors of this review, considering the operationalization present in the analyzed articles in relation to the identified variables. This categorization, however, was not always straightforward.

As shown in Table 1, work incidents and accidents are the most frequently represented negative indicators in the analyzed studies, followed by injury rates. Conversely, safety behaviors emerged as the most commonly cited positive indicator in the literature, followed by factors such as safety culture, safety compliance, and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) (Table 2).

Some variables were classified as either safety-promoting or error-inducing, depending on how they were evaluated/operationalized by the authors of the reviewed articles. This includes the variables task design, physical environment, and safety performance (this issue will be discussed in greater detail in the discussion section).

Table 1. Safety performance indicators identified in the literature review related to Error enforcing factors

Variables to assess safety performance	Studies	Conceptualization of the variables (according to the authors)
Accidents	Eskandari et al. (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “An occupational accident is an occurrence in the course of work causing physical or mental occupational injury (Hughes & Ferrett, 2016)” (p. 380) * <p>The authors conducted a qualitative study. Eleven organizational factors' sub-themes were identified (e.g., management commitment and participation, employee involvement, etc.). The participants considered these factors as effective on occupational accidents.</p>

	Tong et al. (2020b)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “In the 2-4 Model, the accident causes are divided into two levels, the individual level and the organizational level, and they are also attributed to four stages: direct causes (DC), indirect causes (IC), radical causes (RAC) and root causes (ROC). The DC of accidents are unsafe acts and conditions. The IC are poor individual factors. Defects or miscommunication in the safety management system (SMS) are considered the RAC” (p. 2) • “(...) accidents are multicausal, and different combinations of causal factors lead to different accidents. The accurate identification of the causal factors can provide guidance for the mitigation of unsafe acts and the control of unsafe conditions, which positively impacts accident prevention” (p. 6)
	Wang & Yan (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The “improved accident causation model, which demonstrates the relationships among different causal factors (...) provides a pathway for accident analysis from the individual level to the organizational level. Unsafe acts and conditions, determined by individuals’ poor safety knowledge, low safety awareness, bad safety habits, etc., are the immediate causes of an accident. Deficiencies in SMS and safety culture (SC) remain the root causes, which can cause consequences at the individual level” (p. 1)
	Wang et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “(...) The 24Model (...) is chosen as the tool for the analysis of this hazardous chemical accident (...). Here, “2” means causes at the individual level and organizational level; “4” means the causes classification, including unsafe acts and unsafe conditions, flaws in habitual behaviors, deficiencies in SMS, weaknesses in SC (...). The 24Model indicates that all accidents belong to the organization and are mainly attributed to internal organizational causes (at both individual and organizational levels) (Fu et al., 2005; 2018) (p. 3/4)
	Zhao et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “SP is measured through accident indicators” (p. 8) • This article provides a detailed analysis of the types of accidents occurring in construction in China, including falling injuries, collapses, and other types of accidents. The data presented show the percentages of different types of accidents each year, allowing for an analysis of the prevalence and trends of accidents over time. This provides a quantitative view of SP by monitoring the frequency and types of accidents that occurred.
Incidents	Kannan et al. (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The term incident has various applications such as human safety, environmental impact, uncontrolled release of product and operation beyond design limit (Guy Desjardins, 2012). Incidents may also be defined more specifically by a regulator in a particular jurisdiction such as the environmental protection agency in US, which defines incident as a work related event where an injury, ill health (regardless of severity) or fatality occurred or could have occurred (EPA, 2016). The incidents in this work broadly can be categorized under the aforementioned definitions, with a focus on process safety related upsets.” (p. 172)
	Pickup et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Incident type: (1) <i>Accidents</i> – involves the respondent who had direct control of the incident either through action or inaction. The event caused actual harm to self, another person or equipment; (2) <i>Near misses</i> – involves the respondent who had direct control of the incident either through their action or inaction. The event nearly caused harm to self, another person or equipment; (3) <i>Unsafe acts</i> – actions within the workplace that have occurred without incident, i.e. did not nearly / cause an accident but are nonetheless considered unsafe by the participant; (4) <i>Unsafe conditions</i> – relates to descriptions of environmental conditions in the workplace that have the potential to cause harm to self or others.” (p. 4)
	Probst et al. (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The OSHA (2018) defines a recordable incident as any work-related injury or illness that results in death, loss of consciousness, days away from work, restricted job duty or transfer, or medical treatment beyond first aid). The recordable incidence rates represents the number of annual work-related injuries and illnesses per 100 full-time workers (i.e., 40 h./wk., 50 wk./yr.) and is calculated using the following formula: $(N/EH) \times 200,000$, where N = the number of injuries or illnesses recorded in the company’s OSHA log, EH = total hours worked by all employees during the calendar year and the value 200,000 is used as base number of hours for 100 equivalent full-time workers.” (p. 47)
	Qayoom & Hadikusumo (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Incident rate → No. of incidents per month” (p. 2340)
	Stemn et al. (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Incidence rate: (...) frequency of less severe injuries such as medical treated injuries and restricted work injuries (...), fatalities and lost time injuries. (...) The monthly incidence (total reportable injury) rates of each of the sites for each one hundred workers employed were computed based on the Australian Standard (1990) for workplace injury and disease recording.” (p. 349)
	Tang et al. (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Incidents are culmination of risks that often go unheeded due to defective monitoring mechanism (...).” (p. 44) • “In the third section, the respondents were required to rate the probability of incident occurrence due to failure or negligence in observing the indicators on the Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 representing increasing probability.” (p. 46)
Injury rates	Dennerlein et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The other main outcomes utilized for the study were the recordable injury rate (...) (worksites’ hours worked; OSHA reportable injuries; injuries resulting in days away, restricted or transferred -DART). We calculated injury rates (...) by the

		number of medical treatment cases divided by total hours worked then multiplied by 200 000 to obtain the injury rate per 100 full-time equivalent (FTE). Similarly, we calculated DART rates by the number of lost and restricted workday cases divided by total work hours then multiplied by 200 000 to obtain the number of DART cases per 100 FTE." (p. 3)
	Ghodrati et al. (2018)	• "(...) The second section collects project-specific data for SP, such as recordable injuries and lost time injuries." (p. 110)
	Marín et al. (2017)	• "Injuries were estimated through a 3-year injury rate, defined as the total number of claims per 100 workers. Based on this rate, potential participating companies were stratified into three groups (low, medium and high injury rates). The average injury rate for the entire construction sector in Colombia (...) (8.5 injuries per 100 workers) was used to define the cut-off points (...). Participating companies with a 3-year injury rate of less than 8.5 were classified in the "low" category, those twice the average (17.0) were classified as "high" and "medium" otherwise." (p. 3)
Risk index	Boukas & Kontogiannis (2019)	• "The overall risk potential can be calculated by taking the product of human error impact, risky behavior, and unsafe actions. Given that risk has always an initial value, the current value of the risk potential can be calculated as follows: Risk potential / Initial risk = coef × Unsafe conditions × Risky behavior × Human error impact, where risk potential varies in a scale from 1 to 100 and unsafe conditions and risky behavior vary in a scale from 0 to 1." (p. 5)
Risk level	Qayoom & Hadikusumo (2019)	• "A conceptual causal-loop diagram is constructed (...) to establish the relationship between SC components and the factors associated with SP (e.g. risk level)" (p. 2326) "Risk Level = INTEG(probability of risk – safety control measures, 5)" (p. 2335)
	Tong et al. (2020a)	• "Project risk, as one of the leading indicators of SP, measures the risk level of construction project (...). The occurrence of project risk is closely related to the lack of integrated SMS of the company and the failure of relevant agencies to assume their safety responsibility." (p. 1) • Assessment of project risk: (1) <i>Development project risk</i> (e.g., work environment, etc.); (2) <i>Commercial project risk</i> (fire safety, natural disaster, etc.); (3) <i>Residential project risk</i> (e.g., high-risk operation, traffic safety, etc.) (p. 7)
Risk tolerance	Salas et al. (2020)	• "(...) risk tolerance is defined as an individual's subjective understanding of and behavior regarding danger that could possibly lead to injury." (p.1) In this study, the evaluation of SP is done through specific risk tolerance indicators, like <i>affective association</i> (e.g., accident reaction, coworker/friend work-related injuries), <i>control belief</i> (e.g., multitasking, dangerous activities), <i>societal view</i> (e.g., country, productivity before safety), <i>safety culture</i> (e.g., following rules and procedures, equipment and tools availability) and <i>attitude to risk-taking</i> (e.g., risk-taking behavior, risk choices) (p.6)
Risk behaviors	Low et al. (2019)	• "Risk-taking is a type of unsafe behavior that involves making a decision with uncertainty in both the probability of failure/success and its associated severity" (p. 2). E.g.: "During the past 12 months: you have always worked without using the required PPE, tools, or other working equipment?; you have always refused to wear safety goggles and earplugs during cutting and hammering?" (p. 4)
Human error	Pickup et al. (2020)	• "(1) <i>Poor planning / risk assessment</i> (e.g., conscious decision making); (2) <i>Distractions</i> (e.g., physical and psychological distractions where attention was divided or focused on a task with little awareness of external environments and events); (3) <i>Rule breaking</i> (e.g., knowingly not using the correct equipment or following set procedures)" (p. 5)
Personnel error behavior	Çakit et al. (2020)	• "The main objective of this study was to integrate the structural equation modeling with an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system approach for modeling SC in the petrochemical industry in terms of (...) personnel error behavior." (p. 2) "Personnel error behavior (e.g.): I intentionally bend formal procedures to finish work on time; I have ignored some parts of procedures and do not record these to make work easier in abnormal circumstances." (p. 5)
Supervisor violations	Pickup et al. (2020)	• "Explicit descriptions of supervisor deviations from known rules or safe practices, such as operating machinery when untrained (e.g., "Supervisor jumps onto a FLT... he does not have a FLT License!")" (p. 5)
Unsafe conditions/hazards	Qayoom & Hadikusumo (2019)	• A conceptual causal-loop diagram is constructed using the group model building approach to establish the relationship between SC components and the factors associated with SP (e.g., unsafe conditions) (p. 2326) "Unsafe conditions → Cumulative no. of unsafe conditions at 12th month" (p. 2340)
Unsafe acts/behavior	Qayoom & Hadikusumo (2019)	• A conceptual causal-loop diagram is constructed using the group model building approach to establish the relationship between SC components and the factors associated with SP (e.g., unsafe acts) (p. 2326) • "Unsafe acts → No. of unsafe acts per month" (p. 2340)
Task design	Pickup et al. (2020)	• "Describes suitability of: (1) tasks or equipment, including differences in equipment, (2) the ease at which an individual can successfully complete the task, (3) non-standard tasks, unusual / novel situation, ergonomically challenging, (4) how operations planned are immediate preconditions to active failures that can be derived from higher order latent conditions at the organisational level such as

Physical environment	Pickup et al. (2020)	resource management or organisational climate" (e.g., "stack and positioned it too far over, poor visibility didn't help"; "welding above head height"). (p. 5) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Captures scenarios that described the role of the immediate environment the task was conducted in, for example: (1) heating, lighting, space, physical hazards (obstacles), (2) floor space and segregation of pedestrians and vehicles / shared workspaces, (3) surfaces, restrictions / poor access, storage of materials (e.g., "narrowly missed a facial injury from a scrap chute that was hanging down"; "slipped on a small pool of oil")" (p. 5)
Safety performance	Kim et al. (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "SP was measured by asking respondents for information about their safety actions in terms of the magnitude of satisfaction with: (a) the number of individual hazards; (b) damage to materials; (c) the motivation of workers; and (d) lost time or absenteeism." (p. 52)

*Note: In this column, whenever the conceptualization of the indicators is not from the authors of the article under review, the reference to the original authors on whom they are based is provided.

Table 2. Safety performance indicators identified in the literature review related to Safety promoting factors

Variables to assess safety performance	Studies	Conceptualization of the variables (according to the authors)
Safety behaviors	Dale et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "The workers' perceptions of safety were measured by five safety climate and behavior scales across different levels of the project organization: (...) safety behaviors of co-workers (8 items) (Brondino et al., 2012) *; (4) perceptions of their own safety behaviors (6 items) (Neal & Griffin, 2006); and (5) specific safety behaviors of their crews (6 items) (Kaskutas et al., 2010). The safety behaviors of coworker items addressed worker perceptions of coworker's general attitude toward safety (i.e. care about others safety awareness); crew behavior items referred to specific behaviors (i.e. use proper personal protective equipment (hard hats and safety glasses) at all times)." (p. 3)
	Hadikusumo et al. (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this article, safety work behaviors (SWB) are evaluated using a Bayesian Belief Network model. This model allows for the assessment of the probability of SWB based on various organizational variables. Specifically, the evaluation of SWB involves collecting data on the mentioned organizational variables (such as SC, communication, empowerment, etc.) and using this data to calculate the probability of the occurrence of safe behaviors.
	Mohammadfam et al. (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "(...) at the end of the questionnaire, a question with three answers (seldom, sometimes, never) was asked about the manner by which the employee deals with the safety regulations, procedures, and norms to assess the safety behavior of the employee." (p. 38)
	Patel & Jha (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "(...) this study can adopt safe work behavior of workers and SP of projects as latent factors in the safety system" (p. 3) • "Work behavior (WB): I follow all the safety procedures for the jobs that I perform (WB1); All workers and employees follow all the safety procedures for the jobs that they perform (WB2)" (p. 5)
	Qayoom & Hadikusumo (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "A conceptual causal-loop diagram is constructed using the group model building approach to establish the relationship between SC components and the factors associated with SP (e.g. safety behavior)" (p. 2326) • "Rate of safe behavior = 0.062 × Worker competence + 0.053 × Safety compliance – 0.014 × "No. of unsafe acts" + 61.235" (p. 2335)
	Zaira & Hadikusumo (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Safety Behaviour: (I1) Safety Awareness; (I2) Safety competency; (I3) Safety understanding; (G1) Peers who actively care; (G2) Sharing safety concerns; (G3) Working safely together" (p. 127)
	Zhang et al. (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "In order to measure the performance level of construction workers' safety behaviors, another two factors are identified and selected: personal safety score (B1) and team safety score (B2). Specifically, B1 records the average of each respondent's safety scores during the last three months, whereas B2 records the average safety score of the respondent's working team. These two factors are evaluated by a five-point scale ("1" stands for a low performance level, and "5" stands for a high performance level)." (p. 4)
Violation behavior	Çakıt et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "The main objective of this study was to integrate the structural equation modeling with an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system approach for modeling SC in the petrochemical industry in terms of violation behavior (...)" (p. 2) "Violation behavior (e.g.): I feel it is essentially important to maintain safety at all times; I believe safety in the workplace is a key issue" (p. 5)
Personnel safety motivation	Çakıt et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "The main objective of this study was to integrate the structural equation modeling with an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system approach for modeling SC in the petrochemical industry in terms (...) personnel safety motivation (...)" (p. 2) "Personnel safety motivation (e.g.): I am capable of following all safety regulations and procedures; It is clear to me how to follow work safety rules and procedures" (p. 5)

Indicators to assess safety performance: A literature review on safety culture in industry and construction sectors

Safety maturity	Karakhan et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Safety maturity is defined by the authors as a quality that represents the level of experience, responsibility, interdependence, and reliability within an organization and at different levels (project, team, and individual) with respect to occupational safety and health. It reflects the maturity of the organization, the resiliency of the production system, and the competence of the workforce.” (p. 2) The empirical evaluation of safety maturity was based on the analysis of criteria defined from the literature and the application of a benefit-cost analysis (Choosing by Advantages - CBA) methodology that considered both leading and lagging safety indicators, as well as other pertinent factors (e.g., safety and supervisory personnel, system maturity and resiliency, etc.)
Safety culture/climate	Dale et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The workers’ perceptions of safety were measured by five safety climate and behavior scales across different levels of the project organization: (1) perception of safety climate of the general contractor (10 items); (2) safety climate of their subcontractor (11 items) (adapted from Zohar & Luria, 2005) (...)” (p. 3)
	Jiang et al. (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The authors evaluate SP using questionnaires that measure correlations between SC, management systems, knowledge, awareness, and habits. This method quantifies safety perceptions and practices, emphasizing qualitative employee perceptions and behaviors rather than predefined quantitative indicators. SC acts as a key indicator influencing the other components, thus serving as a central aspect of SP evaluation in the study. • “Summarization of questionnaire of SC: (1) the importance of safety; (2) the degree to which casualties can be prevented; (3) safety creates economic benefits; (4) the degree of safety integration into corporate management; (5) Safety is mainly determined by safety awareness.” (p. 4)
Safety culture awareness	Kim et al. (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Several researchers identified an interactive relationship between personal, situational and behavior factors in a model of SC (...). These three factors (person, situation, and behavior) were considered as the elements for a SC framework and were determined as the SC awareness of worker (personal), the SMS (situational) and worker behavior (behavioral). The norm system (...) influence the behavior of workers and are determined by the awareness that performing (or not performing) a particular behavior has certain consequences, and the feeling of responsibility for performing a specific behavior” (p. 24)
	Kim et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “In this study, the SC awareness of workers was measured through case studies, TMI accident and Fukushima accident. (...) A framework that consists of four elements including a norm system, a SMS, the worker SC awareness, and workers’ behaviors was used” (p. 307).
Safety compliance	Curcuruto et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The association of safety climate dimensions with safe work performance is an essential element for validating safety climate tools in new industrial contexts. Past safety research (...) has emphasized the association of safety climate dimensions with two main categories of work conduct (Griffin & Neal, 2000): safety compliance and safety participation. Safety compliance refers to the behaviours that are about engaging in core safety tasks, such as compliance with the organization’s safety rules and regulations, and following safety procedures.” (p. 3/4) • “Safety compliance (e.g.): “I believe it is important to always use safe/standard work procedures”.” (p. 5)
	Kalteh et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “In this study, (...) two other measures of safety compliance and safety participation (Neal & Griffin, 2006) were used. The correlation between safety compliance and safety participation and SC factors has been confirmed (Kalteh et al., 2019).” (p. 4)
Safety participation	Curcuruto et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “(...) safety participation refers to employee’s voluntary participation in safety activities, which aims to contribute to the development of a supportive safety environment.” (p. 4) • “Safety participation (e.g.): “I put in extra effort to improve the safety of the workplace”.” (p. 5)
	Kalteh et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this study, (...) two other measures of safety compliance and safety participation (Neal & Griffin, 2006) were used. The correlation between safety compliance and safety participation and SC factors has been confirmed (Kalteh et al., 2019).” (p. 4)
Management commitment to safety	Pickup et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Implicit / indirect descriptions of supervisors and leader’s day to day commitment and priority toward safety (...): encourage / discourage the reporting of accidents; down grading of incidents; by-passing rules to avoid accident reports; learn from incidents and near misses; willingness or unwillingness to take ownership of safety concerns / poor accountability; etc.” (p. 5)
Use of personal protection equipment (PPE)	Pickup et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Availability of (1) PPE and equipment, first aid equipment; (2) Maintenance of PPE and equipment.” (e.g., “correct gloves - non in welding bay”) (p. 5)
	Wong et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “(...) develop an integrated framework that can help acquire a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and the reasons for the use and non-use of PPE amongst construction workers. (...) four main categories of responses were collected from the participants, namely, (a) general information on previous experiences of the use and non-use of PPE at work, (b) causes of the use and non-use of PPE at work (i.e. personal factors), (c) causes of the use and non-use of PPE at work (i.e. organisational factors) and (d) consequences of the non-use of PPE at work.” (p. 2)

Task design	Pickup et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Describes suitability of: (1) tasks or equipment, including differences in equipment, (2) the ease at which an individual can successfully complete the task, (3) non-standard tasks, unusual / novel situation, ergonomically challenging, (4) how operations are planned are immediate preconditions to active failures that can be derived from higher order latent conditions at the organisational level such as resource management or organisational climate” (e.g., “stack and positioned it too far over, poor visibility didn’t help”; “forks on FLT’s are too short”).” (p. 5)
Physical environment	Pickup et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Captures scenarios that described the role of the immediate environment the task was conducted in, for example: (1) heating, lighting, space, physical hazards (obstacles), (2) floor space and segregation of pedestrians and vehicles / shared workspaces, (3) surfaces, restrictions / poor access, storage of materials” (e.g., “narrowly missed a facial injury from a scrap chute that was hanging down”; “slipped on a small pool of oil”) (p. 5)
Safety performance	Patel & Jha (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “(...) this study can adopt safe work behavior of workers and safety performance of projects as latent factors in the safety system (...)” (p. 3) “SP: I am satisfied with the SP of my project (SP1); How do you rate overall SP of the project? (SP2); In my opinion, my project can achieve the status of the zero-incident project (SP3)” (p. 5)

*Note: In this column, whenever the conceptualization of the indicators is not from the authors of the article under review, the reference to the original authors on whom they are based is provided.

4. Discussion

This literature review aimed to identify indicators to operationalize SP. The identified indicators can be categorized into safety promoting factors (positive indicators) and error enforcing factors (negative indicators). Error enforcing measures were used in 27 studies (e.g., Eskandari et al., 2017; Low et al., 2019; Stemn et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020), and safety promoting measures were used in 24 studies (e.g., Dale et al., 2020; Çakit et al., 2020; Mohammadfam et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2016) (considering that some studies included both positive and negative indicators).

One way to evaluate SP is the analysis of safety data through indicators such as *work accidents* (Eskandari et al., 2017; Tong et al., 2020b; Wang & Yan, 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2018), *incidents* (Kannan et al., 2016; Pickup et al., 2020; Probst et al., 2019); Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019; Stemn et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2017), *injury rates* (Dennerlein et al., 2020; Ghodrati et al., 2018; Marín et al., 2017), *risk level* (Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019; Tong et al., 2020a) and *risk index* (Boukas & Kontogiannis, 2019). These indicators provide a standard measurement from various other causes and contextual aspects. They aim to disseminate statistics that enable organizations to measure their SP and make comparisons with other organizations (Shaikh et al., 2021). Although some authors confirmed that these variables have a significant impact on SP and are good indicators of SC outcomes, the use of this type of objective data is complex, given the imprecise, unstable, insensitive, and devaluing nature of risk exposure (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2007). According to the cited authors, such indicators may be misrepresented for various reasons that have little to do with SC (e.g., not reporting incidents due to the existence of incentive schemes; reservations regarding accident reporting; and long periods without accidents, which may suppress accident reporting), therefore may not be very reliable on their own.

Risk tolerance (Salas et al., 2020), *risk behaviors* (Low et al., 2019), *human error* (Pickup et al., 2020), *personnel error behavior* (Çakit et al., 2020), *supervisor violations* (Pickup et al., 2020), *unsafe conditions/hazards* (Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019), *unsafe acts/behavior* (Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019) were also identified in the literature review as relevant indicators of SP. Risk behaviors are actions or omissions on the part of workers that increase the likelihood of accidents or incidents occurring (e.g., working

without wearing the necessary personal protective equipment; skipping steps in standard operating procedures to save time or effort; using machines or tools improperly) (Low et al. 2019; Patel & Jha, 2016; Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019). These behaviors violate safety standards and procedures, exposing workers to unnecessary dangers (Low et al. 2019). It should be noted that when these behaviors are not identified and corrected, they can become normal, leading to a work environment in which safety is neglected. As for risk tolerance, it is defined as a personal assessment of risk, encompassing feelings of comfort or discomfort given the risk (Salas et al., 2020). Given its subjective nature, it is difficult to define, measure, and manage in a clear and concise manner. It is driven by reasons linked to job attributes (e.g., type of work), personal characteristics (e.g., affective associations, exposure history, and feelings of control), perceived consequences (e.g., likelihood of injury or death), and social and cultural factors (e.g., economic outlook, skepticism, and SC) (Salas et al., 2020). Human error encompasses incidents caused by skill-based and perceptual errors, rule-based mistakes, violations, and events beyond the individuals' control (referred to as "non-intentional") (Pickup et al., 2020). This includes poor planning, distractions and rule-breaking, all of which contribute to incidents and accidents in the workplace, and therefore, to a poor SP. The same goes for personnel error behavior, as they represent failures to adhere to safety procedures (Çakit et al., 2020). For example, if a worker ignores parts of procedures to make their work easier, such behavior increases the risk of accidents.

Supervisor violations are understood as failures or disrespect for safety rules and procedures on the part of supervisors. These behaviors not only increase safety risks directly, but also create an environment where workers may feel less obliged to follow safety rules, resulting in a weaker SC and increasing the risk of incidents and accidents (Çakit et al., 2020; Pickup et al., 2020; Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019).

Unsafe acts/behavior and conditions/hazards are directly related to the occurrence of occupational accidents (Tong et al., 2020b; Wang et al., 2020; Wang & Yan, 2019). Unsafe acts or behaviors include risky decisions and actions that ignore safety procedures, contributing to the occurrence of accidents and incidents, while unsafe conditions refer to the physical environment that can cause harm, such as faulty equipment or hazards in the workplace (Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019). The results of research seeking to understand the cause of accidents highlight the influence of worker's unsafe acts on accident-related unsafe conditions. Identifying and eliminating these unsafe acts is crucial for accident prevention (Wang et al., 2020).

From a safety promoting perspective, this literature review allowed the identification of indicators such as *safety behaviors* (Dale et al., 2020; Hadikusumo et al., 2017; Mohammadfam et al., 2017; Patel & Jha, 2016; Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019; Zaira & Hadikusumo, 2017; Zhang et al., 2016), *violation behavior* (Çakit et al., 2020), *personnel safety motivation* (Çakit et al., 2020), *safety maturity* (Karakhan et al., 2018), *safety climate/culture* (Dale et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2019), *safety culture awareness* (Kim et al., 2017; 2018), *safety compliance* (Curcuruto et al., 2018; Kalteh et al., 2020), *safety participation* (Curcuruto et al., 2018; Kalteh et al., 2020), *management commitment* (Pickup et al., 2020), and *use of personal protective equipment* (Pickup et al., 2020; Wong et al., 2020). By focusing on these safety promoting factors, organizations can identify and mitigate potential risks, reduce the likelihood of accidents and injuries, and promote a culture of safety within the organization.

Safety behaviors include not only workers' compliance with safety rules and procedures, but also their safety initiatives (Dale et al., 2020; Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014; Low et al., 2019; Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019). These behaviors encompass compliance with minimum standards of safety at work (e.g., adherence to safety procedures, use of PPE, and accomplishing work in a safe manner), which contribute to the improvement of workers' health and safety. Safety behaviors also support the organization's safety goals and objectives (e.g., helping co-workers, promoting work safety programs, participating in voluntary safety activities, and improving work safety). Therefore, they involve organizational citizenship behaviors (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014).

Regarding the variable violation behavior, although violation behaviors are generally seen as negative indicators, since they involve disobedience to rules and safety procedures, Çakıt et al. (2020) description of the importance of maintaining safety and encouraging others to use safety practices is understood, from our perspective, as a positive approach to reducing violations (e.g., "I feel it is essentially important to maintain safety at all times"; "I believe safety in the workplace is a key issue"). For this reason, we chose to integrate this variable into the positive indicators, as it follows a safety promoting direction.

Safety maturity and safety motivation are also associated with safety promoting behaviors. Safety maturity is associated with the degree of experience, responsibility, interdependence, and trust within an organization regarding occupational safety and health at different levels: project, team, and individual level (Karakhan et al., 2018). As such, it can be an imperative indicator of SP, and should ideally be measured by the total level of maturity (organizational, systemic, and behavioral). The resilience of the system and the competence of the workers reflect the maturity of the organization (Karakhan et al., 2018). Safety motivation refers to the willingness of organizational members to adopt safety behaviors (Boukas & Kontogiannis, 2019; Çakıt et al., 2020; Hadikusumo et al., 2017). Workers tend to be motivated to comply with safe work practices and participate in safety activities when they perceive a positive safety climate in the workplace. When they are not safety-motivated, there is a greater tendency to be non-compliant with safety regulations and negligent of work-related hazards (Al-Bayati, 2021; Neal & Griffin, 2006). Safety motivation can be reinforced through penalties, peer pressure, and incentive programs.

Another key indicator of SP is safety culture/climate (Tong et al., 2020a). The assessment of safety culture/climate is understood as an indirect assessment of the resilience of the safety system, providing indications about SP (Shaikh et al., 2021). A positive safety culture/climate is associated with fewer workplace accidents and injuries (Ahmad et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2019; Kalteh et al., 2018; Siuta et al., 2022; Tetzlaff et al., 2021). It is also worth highlighting the importance of SC awareness, which refers to the level of understanding and commitment of employees and management to safety practices in the workplace. It involves promoting behaviors and attitudes that value and prioritize safety (Kim et al., 2017; 2018; Wang & Yan, 2019; Wong et al., 2020). A heightened awareness of SC leads to a significant reduction in the occurrence of accidents and incidents, promoting work satisfaction, well-being and compliance with safety procedures and regulations.

In regard to safety compliance and participation, safety compliance involves actions that focus on adhering to essential safety tasks, such as following the company's safety guidelines and protocols (Curcuruto et al., 2018; Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014, 2017).

Conversely, safety participation pertains to employees willingly taking part in safety-related activities to help foster a supportive and safe work environment (Curcuruto et al., 2018; Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014, 2017).

On the same token, it is important to emphasize management commitment importance in improving SP (Curcuruto et al., 2018; Shaikh et al., 2021). Workers are more likely to improve their working conditions and comply with safety standards and procedures when they feel that management takes keen interest in their safety. This commitment should be reflected not only in the attitudes of management, but also in its visible and observable acts and behaviors (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014).

Regarding the use of PPE, the literature points its key role in decreasing the risk of workplace injuries and accidents (Kannan et al., 2016; Wong et al., 2020; Zaira & Hadikusumo, 2017). It is imperative for organizations to invest in safety resources and PPE, training, and guidance on the use of safety equipment, so that they are able to deal with injury prevention strategies and recognize hazards in their workplaces (Shaikh et al., 2021).

Some variables identified in this review were categorized as either safety-promoting or error-inducing based on how the authors of the reviewed articles evaluated / operationalized them. These variables include *task design*, *physical environment*, and *safety performance*. Regarding task design, Pickup et al. (2020) emphasize that an adequate task design, which considers ergonomics and ease of safe task execution, is crucial for preventing active failures and accidents. A well-designed task promotes safety and is therefore a positive indicator. However, if poorly designed, it can be a negative indicator, inducing errors and compromising the safety system. The same logic applies to the physical environment. The physical environment includes factors such as lighting, space, obstacles, and adequate access (Pickup et al., 2020). A safe and well-planned physical environment is a positive indicator, promoting safety. Conversely, a hazardous and poorly planned physical environment is a negative indicator, inducing errors and accidents (Qayoom & Hadikusumo, 2019). As for safety performance, although it is a positive indicator, reflecting the effectiveness of safety practices and the reduction of incidents and accidents in the workplace (cf., Patel & Jha, 2016), it was measured in a negative context by Kim et al. (2019) (e.g., absenteeism, damage to materials, etc.). Therefore, SP can be seen as both a positive and negative indicator, depending on the perspective adopted.

The identified indicators, both positive and negative, reflect the complexity of measuring SP and the necessity of a comprehensive approach. They provide a comprehensive framework for assessing and improving SP in organizations, especially in the industrial and construction sectors, where pressure for productivity can often compromise safety. Positive indicators, such as safety behaviors, safety motivation and management commitment, are essential for creating and maintaining a robust SC (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2007; 2014; Çakit et al., 2020). Promoting these indicators can lead to a significant reduction in accidents and incidents at work, as well as improving worker satisfaction and well-being. On the other hand, the indicators categorized as negative, such as risky behavior and supervisor violations, highlight critical areas that need urgent intervention. Identifying and mitigating these factors is key to preventing accidents and creating a safer working environment (Bai & Liu, 2023; Golabchi et al., 2024; Lingard et al., 2017). Identifying and continuously monitoring these indicators allows organizations not only to measure their SP, but also to implement proactive strategies for continuous

improvement. Using both type of indicators in an integrated way can provide a holistic view of workplace safety, allowing for more effective interventions.

5. Conclusions

The findings of this literature review highlight the importance of considering various SP indicators in the evaluation of occupational safety. The analysis performed contemplated 33 articles, and allowed the identification of 25 SP indicators. These indicators, referred to in literature as positive and negative, highlight the challenges involved in assessing SP and the importance of employing a multifaceted methodology. The distinction between positive and negative indicators emphasizes the dual focus required in SP management: promoting safety-enhancing behaviors and mitigating error-enforcing factors. Positive indicators, such as safety maturity and safety motivation, highlight areas where the organization is succeeding in fostering SC. Negative indicators, on the other hand, such as accident rates and reported safety violations, indicate areas needing improvement.

Reactive and proactive SP indicators can provide a set of meaningful measures for researchers and practitioners in the construction and industry sectors, by summarizing their benefits and limitations for future applications, to increase SP in these sectors (Shaikh et al., 2021). However, a rigid division between reactive and proactive indicators can be overly simplistic. The effective use of an indicator depends on its context and application. An initially reactive indicator can be employed proactively to prevent future incidents, while a proactive indicator can become merely reactive if not used preventively. Thus, the distinction between reactive and proactive indicators is secondary to the overall effectiveness and utilization of various types of performance indicators.

It is important to reflect that SP evaluation is not limited to the use of indicators alone. The widely accepted and recommended model, reflected in ISO 45001 (2019) – the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle –, provides a framework for structuring this approach. The PDCA cycle involves planning safety objectives and processes (Plan), implementing them (Do), monitoring and measuring performance (Check), and taking actions to continually improve (Act). This structured approach ensures that SP evaluation extends beyond mere indicators, encompassing a holistic process of planning, executing, assessing, and refining safety measures, ensuring a more comprehensive and effective approach to safety management, and promoting a safer and healthier working environment.

Some limitations can be identified in the present study. This literature review was conducted within the scope of studies that focused on occupational SC, which limits its breadth of coverage. The aim of the systematic literature review was not to investigate SP indicators, but rather to explore dimensions of safety culture/climate and SMS that impact SP. Consequently, the selection of keywords used influenced the type of indicators identified. Additionally, the last year of the time period of the articles included in the review (2020) corresponded to an atypical time of the pandemic, which may have introduced some bias. The categorization of the variables identified in the reviewed literature as negative and positive indicators is an interpretation made by the authors of this study, and as such, there may be partiality/disagreement with their classification. In any case, the authors discussed all the most ambiguous situations, and tried to reach a consensus after discussion.

The results of this literature review make a significant contribution to the current, though limited, understanding of SP indicators in construction and industry sectors. The list of SP indicators presented serves as a reference point for future empirical research if considered a balanced approach, which provides a more complete picture of an organization's SC and its effectiveness in preventing workplace accidents and injuries. Organizations should seek to understand whether their current safety policies, practices, and measures are robust enough to continue improving workers' SP. Therefore, future research should analyze the implications of workers' SP and the SP indicators identified in this review by studying their relationship across different organizational cultures. It should be noted that SP indicators necessitate an approach where indicators of various levels (individual, group, organizational), focused on safety management activities and expressing the ability of organizations to develop their activities safely, should be contemplated.

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